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Cleaning GPS trajectories using machine learning techniques

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Abstract

Nowadays, the wide availability of GNSS enabled portable devices, such as smartphones and smart-watches, enables professional athletes and outdoor enthusiasts to track and analyse their activities. However, although the nominal precision of the system is high enough for a precise analysis, various environmental factors can affect it, resulting in incorrect positions that could have a negative impact on the resulting trace. Most of the commercial services providing analysis of outdoor activities offer techniques that can be used to "clean" the uploaded traces. Generally, these techniques exploit the huge amount of data collected by the service, but still manifest problems in their outcomes.

The goal of this thesis project is to investigate the application of machine learning methods to the field of GPS signal processing, identifying areas, without exploiting geographical knowledge, in which a GPS trace could have been affected by a positional error, applying then a correcting technique on the discovered areas. The reason behind the decisions of not exploiting geographical knowledge and big data techniques is twofold. From one side, we aim at developing a technique that can be applied also on low powered devices. On the other hand, we would like to consider also activities which are not constrained by networks of roads or paths (e.g. ski touring or kayaking), for which it would not be possible to apply geographical knowledge.

Firstly, the absence of an already existing dataset containing annotated GPS traces, therefore traces where the errors were explicitly marked, resulted in the development of a web platform used for collecting over 60 traces related to eight different outdoor activities. In our work, we focused on two kinds of errors often present in the recorded traces, namely pauses and positional errors.

Following, the collected data were employed in a comparison of various machine learning techniques on a simple activity recognition task, to understand their ability of modelling GNSS properties. The results of the comparison led us to focus on LSTM based approaches, investigated further in the evaluation of two architectures derived from the literature and a custom proposed one, based on bidirectional LSTM cells. The evaluation of the various techniques was performed on segments obtained by applying a sliding window approach on the collected traces, a strategy that allowed the models to focus on a limited number of points and context, and resulted in the custom architecture obtaining the larger accuracy. The final model, which obtained a mean accuracy of over 0.97, was converted, without performance loss, to a TensorFlow Lite model to enable its execution on low powered mobile devices.

After obtaining a light model able to distinguish between various types of errors, a visual comparison between correcting approaches, including interpolation techniques and Kalman Filters based methods, outlined how a custom bidirectional application of Kalman Filters, on areas marked as positional errors, performed the best. On the other hand, the detected pauses were removed and replaced by the mean position of the recorded points, since they represent a situation in which the user's position was stationary. This approach was so selected and combined, along with the trained model, in a light Python package released on GitHub under the name of GPSClean.

Further developments of this project could include an expansion of the used dataset, both in terms of number of traces and location in which they have been collected, since most of them were

recorded in the Trentino-South Tyrol region. Furthermore, the usage of traces metadata, such as the activity type and device, could be investigated. Moreover, other machine learning approaches could be included in the comparison and the definition of an objective metric to assess the quality of a GPS trace, which is still an open question, could allow a more objective comparison of the correcting techniques.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Nowadays, a wide range of portable devices, such as smartphones, smartwatches and fitness trackers, contains a GPS sensor able to determine the position of the device, and hence the user, in real time. The availability of such a sensor enables various use cases and applications, for example navigation using a map application, finding a lost device but also simply tracking user's location through time, a functionality exploited by both professional and amateur athletes, which results in what is generally referred to as a GPS trace. Moreover, more business-oriented applications of GPS related technologies can include, for example, fleet tracking.

However, the position recorded by the GPS sensor, thanks to the signals received by four different satellites out of the GPS satellites' constellation [1], is not always completely accurate. Actually, data reported by the U.S. Government, official maintainer of the GPS satellites constellation, reports how, for example, the actual position of a smartphone is on average within a 4.9 meters radius from the registered one [2], under open sky circumstances. Clearly, such an error could not impact significantly some applications of this technology.

Nevertheless, in some cases, the error of the recorded position could be larger, for example in situations in which the reception of the signal is worsened by external factors, such as when obstacles reflect the received signal, a circumstance known as canyon effect [3]. This situation does not arise only in the wild nature, and it is often reproduced in cities where tall buildings "limit" the capability of the sensor to obtain a clear signal, worsening so its precision.

The aforementioned examples outline how it is not unlikely to obtain an incorrect position, which can then result in an incorrect GPS trace. Different studies have hence concentrated their attention on correcting techniques that can be applied on an already collected GPS trace, trying so to enhance it and remove imperfections and errors.

Some of them (for example [4], [5]) based their techniques on historical data, hence past trajectories, or pre-determined routes to identify outliers and correct them. Alternatively, the application of fixed constraints was also considered [6] along with machine learning techniques, which were employed mostly on data coming from vehicles ([7] and [8]).

Most of the conducted studies focused either on the application of quite fixed constraints, which could not suit a wide range of applications, or employed historical data related to a certain area or collected while following a quite predictable route (for example a vehicle travelling on a specific street), making so more difficult to generalise the adopted techniques. Furthermore, relying often on big data techniques, the developed methods cannot generally be applied on low powered devices.

1.2 Our contribution

The goal of this thesis' project is to contribute to the field of GPS traces correcting techniques, investigating the application of machine learning methods in the identification of errors in traces collected while performing outdoor sport activities, without applying any specific knowledge on the area in which the traces were collected, obtaining so a general model. Additionally, we aim for a model able to run also on low powered devices, enabling so errors' recognition also on mobile portable devices, at the level of edge computing.

The choice of using traces collected while performing outdoor sport activities derived from the intention of having traces which could contain a wide range of changes in the direction or speed, changes that are not usually present in traces collected by vehicles or pedestrians in urban contexts. Moreover, ignoring any possible information about the area in which a trace was collected allows a level of generalisation useful to apply the same model on traces collected in different areas.

As an additional contribution, a dataset containing 61 annotated GPS traces, namely traces where various types of errors were marked, was collected and used then in the training of a supervised machine learning model, resulting from the first part of the research. The data collection part was necessary, given the fact that most publicly available GPS traces datasets do not contain any particular annotation on the errors.

As mentioned previously, the first part of the research concerned the training of a supervised machine learning model able to identify various types of errors in a GPS trace. A comparison between various machine learning techniques on a simple activity recognition task brought us to focus on LSTM-based approaches and, after a comparison of different architectures on a subset of the collected dataset, to the adoption of a particular architecture based on bidirectional LSTM cells. The goal of this section of the research was to narrow then the application of a selected correcting technique, minimising so the modifications performed to correct points.

The second part of the research focused on correcting techniques that can be applied on the identified errors. Various techniques were compared on randomly selected traces, and a customised bidirectional variation of Kalman Filters was considered for the correction of positional errors, with points detected as a pause being removed and replaced by their mean position, representing so a stationary situation.

The resulting model and correcting techniques were then joined together in a single lightweight Python package, named GPSClean, which makes available an easy-to-use single pipeline to perform the correction of a GPS trace, without the need of manually running the project's code.

In our work, we focused on the Global Positioning System (GPS), for simplicity reasons. However, similar considerations and approaches can be applied also to other satellite systems.

We can so summarise the contributions of this project as follows:

- collection of an annotated dataset of outdoor activities for data repair
- evaluation of different machine learning architectures for GNNS data classification
- development and evaluation of a machine learning model for detecting errors in GNNS traces
- evaluation and development of algorithms for correcting errors detected in GNNS traces
- implementation of the selected techniques in a lightweight Python package

1.3 The structure of the thesis

The work undertaken during this thesis' project is presented in the next chapters, starting with a background section which introduces more details about the technology behind the GPS and how

its accuracy can be affected by various factors. Moreover, it presents also a summary of numerous studies in the field and the techniques that were developed during previous researches. Furthermore, a separate subsection provides an overview on how machine learning techniques can be employed to classify sequence data.

After that, chapter 3 presents the development of a web application that was employed during the collection of the annotated GPS traces dataset. In particular, it describes how the web platform offers the possibility to mark specific subsections of a GPS trace as errors, uploading then the result to a database. The technologies employed in the development of the web platform are also analysed.

Following, chapter 4 outlines the modelling phase, the comparison between various architectures and presents the performance of the final model that was employed in the errors' detection phase.

Subsequently, the correction phase is described in chapter 5, along with the variations of various techniques that were experimented and examples of their application. Furthermore, this chapter introduces also the developed all-in-one open source command line application, along with the chosen implementation techniques and a reference to the official GitHub repository.

After that, chapter 6 outlines our conclusions after the project and considers some aspects that could potentially improve the results.

Chapter 2

Backgrounds

2.1 The Global Positioning System

For humans, being able to determine their position on earth and with respect to some locations has always represented a greatly investigated problem.

In the past, people primarily based this process on fixed natural references, such as the sun during the day, to determine the four Cardinal points, and the stars at night (in particular the Pole Star and the Southern Cross respectively).

Over time, technological advancements made available various artificial instruments that could be used for positioning, ranging from the compass to the more recent GPS system.

GPS stands for "Global Positioning System" and is a positioning system developed by the United States of America, through their Department of Defense, during the 1970s and 1980s [1]. Similarly to other technologies (such as the Internet), it was first developed in a controlled environment, in this case the military, before being available to the public, phase that for the GPS occurred at the beginning of the 1990s.

The system is composed of 24 satellites, distributed on different orbits, so that it is always possible to receive the signal of at least 4 satellites, no matter the position of the user [1]. The third component of the system, in addition to the satellites and the user, are the control stations, which monitor precisely the position of each satellite.

Whenever the user would like to calculate his position, the GPS sensor listens to the electromagnetic waves of four different satellites. It then monitors the time taken by the signal to reach the device starting from the satellites and, as it knows the exact position of each satellite, is then able to calculate its position with respect to them. The positions of the satellites are monitored by the control stations, which then propagate the information using a specific registry updated continuously [1].

The requirement of the four different satellites is enforced in order to measure three different coordinates (latitude, longitude and altitude), while the fourth signal is used to synchronise the internal clock of the device [1].

GPS accuracy and the multipath effect

A punctual and timely reception of the GPS signal, transmitted by the satellites in the form of a radio signal, is crucial for a precise calculation of the position of the receiving device. According to a study performed in 2015 [2], the positioning error of the GPS, under open sky circumstances, is generally within 5m when determining the position using a smartphone.

However, the GPS signal, being an electromagnetic wave, can be influenced by the surrounding environment. In particular, the signal can be reflected by a certain surface, resulting in what is known as a multipath [3].

Figure 2.1: The multipath effect. Reproduced from [3]

Clearly, the reflected signal takes longer than the direct path, introducing a delay that could result in a potential error in the calculation of the position. Moreover, given that satellites are constantly moving, the effect of multipath at a certain location changes over time, depending on the position of the satellites [3]. Furthermore, experiments have shown how the multipath effect can introduce an additional average of $8m$ error in the derived position [3].

The described reflection process can so occur in nature, with the reflective surface being, for example, a mountain, resulting in what is known as the *canyon effect*.

Figure 2.2: Example of the canyon effect on a GPS trace recorded, with a Garmin Forerunner 45 ©, during a via ferrata

However, the canyon effect is possible also in urban contexts, with tall buildings substituting the mountains with a similar effect (urban canyons) [9]. Furthermore, the height of the buildings, along with their distance with respect to the receiver, are also influential factors in the received signal and hence on the impact of the multipath effect in urban contexts [10].

2.2 Classifying using machine learning methods

Generally, machine learning methods can be distinguished among the following categories, based on the training method:

- Supervised training: during the training phase, examples with an associated label/categorisation are provided to the model.
- Unsupervised training: in this case, the dataset contains no labelled data and the goal of the algorithm is to find/uncover patterns and structures among the different data points, potentially leading to an automatic categorisation.
- Reinforcement learning: when an agent takes actions in a certain environment with the goal of maximising the rewards obtained as feedback of its behaviour.

In this section, the focus is on supervised training, chosen approach to train a model on the collected annotated dataset, described in section 3.

2.2.1 Supervised learning

More in detail, a supervised learning task starts with a training set containing pairs (x, y) , where x is the training example, belonging to feature space X and y its label, belonging to the target space Y [11].

Generally, the initial dataset is divided into a train and test dataset, with the training part used to train the model weights and the test part for the final evaluation. Additionally, different evaluation techniques can be used, possibly including a separate validation set, used to evaluate the model at the end of each training epoch, or techniques such as cross fold validation, which alternatively use $k - 1$ parts of the dataset for training and one for testing, with k being a specific parameter.

The overall goal of the model is to exploit the training set to minimise a specific error function on the test set [11]. The model, using its weights, tries to compute the output value/prediction for each element of the train set and, comparing it with the true value, adjusts its weights accordingly. The aforementioned process is generally repeated multiple times (epochs) for all training elements. Typically, in a regression task, when a real value is the output of the model, the error function is based on the distance between the predicted and true value. This can be considered, for example, as the mean squared error or the mean absolute error [11]. When working on classification problems, and therefore when the output of the model is a categorisation, the error function, called also *loss function*, is generally the log loss.

2.2.2 Sequence labelling

The data used to train a machine learning model can vary, ranging from single examples containing just some features, to an entire image or a sequence of different features. In the latter case, the problem is recognised as a *sequence labelling* problem, thus a problem where each example is composed of an entire sequence of values and each point is denoted as *time step*. Data belonging to this category of machine learning problems are generally time series [11], but sequences of data can be found also in other fields, such as protein structures in genetic [11].

The problem of labelling sequences of data, closely related to the labelling of GPS data, can be subdivided among the following categories [11]:

- Sequence classification [11]: where the input is a sequence of features and the goal is to assign a label to the entire sequence. For this reason, it is possible to process the complete example before deriving a prediction.
- Segment classification [11]: when the target is a sequence composed by multiple labels, but the positions of the labels are known. A standard technique, when classifying segments, is to apply windowing techniques to derive a context for each considered point. Examples of

applications of segment classification are often found in the Natural Language Processing field.

- Temporal classification [11]: similar to the previous case, since the target is a sequence of labels. However, in temporal classification the position of the labels is not known in advance and hence a separate model is necessary to derive the labels' alignment.

GPS data are represented by sequences of points, and detecting different types of errors inside the sequence led us to a segment classification approach, as explained in section 4.

2.2.3 Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks, a type of machine learning model often used for classification, are networks composed of artificial neurons joined together by weighted connections. Each neuron is a small processing units that receive a certain weighted input, coming from the previous layer, and applies what is known as an *activation function*, namely a function that, based on the input value, determines the signal that will be passed to the following layer. The first layer, known as the *input layer*, receives its values from the feature of the current input example, while the last layer, the *output layer*, represents the output that is expected by the network and therefore the number of output neurons is related to the number of possible output classes/parameters [12].

The layers between the input and output layers are called *hidden layers* and their goal is to apply non-linear transformations to the input, transmitting the resulting values to the output layer, which will return the final classification. The presence of multiple hidden layers forms a so-called *deep neural network*.

Figure 2.3: The structure of a deep neural network. Reproduced from [12]

Recurrent Neural Networks

The output of a standard neural network depends only on the current input, and is therefore not related with past or future inputs. However, in some scenarios and in particular when dealing with segment classification, it is useful to exploit past and future observations, hence the context of the current observation, to generate the prediction.

For this reason, the possibility of having cycles in the connections between neurons should be considered, leading to a particular form of neural network denoted as *recurrent neural network* (RNN). This approach has the advantage of potentially using the entire history of a sequence, up to the current timestamp, to predict the correspondent output, a concept similar to the one of memory for humans [12].

The implementation of this type of network is similar to the one outlined in the previous section for standard neural networks, with a main difference: at each time step, the activations which reach the hidden layer comes both from the current input and the result of the activations of the previous time step [12], as shown in figure 2.4.

When visualised, as done in figure 2.4, recurrent neural networks are generally shown "unfolding" the cycles in the neurons along the input sequence.

Figure 2.4: A representation of the structure of an RNN, in its unfolded version. Reproduced from [12]

Long Short Term Memory - LSTM

However, standard RNNs tend to suffer from a problem known as "vanishing gradients" [13]. This phenomenon consists in the decay that usually affects the influence of a certain input on the next ones, as a result of the cycles present in the network structure. For this reason, the influence of an input example is generally inversely proportional with the number of iterations that occurred after it, resulting in a network that gradually forgets what it had learnt from old examples [13].

Figure 2.5: Illustration of how the influence of a certain input (the darker one) decays in a standard RNN with the number of iterations. Reproduced from [13]

The aforementioned reason led to the development of *Long Short Term Memory* (LSTM) cells, a variation of standard RNN. An LSTM network resembles the structure of a standard recurrent neural network, with each neuron being replaced with an LSTM cell.

This cell, represented also in figure 2.6, is composed of a cell state, used to accumulate knowledge, and an output, input and forget gates used to control updates to the cell state and the output at each step [13].

At each time step, the first phase is to determine which information will be retained from the current cell state, and this operation is performed by the forget gate. Following, some new information needs to be stored in the cell state, replacing what was previously forgotten. The input gate is responsible for this update and determines what information will be updated, performing the change to

Figure 2.7: A representation of bidirectional RNN units, which shows the two hidden layers and their forward/backward connections. Reproduced from [12]

figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: The application of a one dimensional convolution on a flattened matrix. Reproduced from [14]

The core idea is to use convolutional layers to "extract features" from consecutive parts of the sequence, using then this information in a later part of the network. For this reason, convolutional layers are generally then chained with standard fully connected layers before reaching the output layer [14].

Often, convolutional layers are applied, in a multidimensional version, over multidimensional matrixes, such as images. However, the same approach can be adopted also on one dimensional data.

Moreover, an additional layer, called pooling layer, can be used to reduce the size of the vector or matrix resulting from the convolution. More in details, a pooling layer applies a specified technique on a prescribed number of consecutive data points, summarising them with a single value. The two most common pooling techniques are the maximum or average values.

2.3 Related Work

The task of cleaning GPS data, and as a more general case time series, has been widely studied in the literature, with some approaches being tailored specifically to GPS traces.

Overall, the proposed approaches can mostly be grouped in six categories.

2.3.1 Smoothing based techniques

Often approaches like the Moving Average (MA), the AutoRegressive Model (AR), and their combination AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) are used to smooth observations (moving average component), considering also the rate of change of the previous points [6]. The approach is generally applied to the entire series, and the resulting points substitute the original observations.

Another approach that belongs to this category are Kalman Filters [6], which join together the observed value and the predicted one to obtain the final observation. The predicted value of the next observation, represented by a state vector, is based on the covariance and relation of the different components, combined with an external influence and uncertainty [15].

Different studies have explored the use of Kalman filters specifically with GPS data, proposing different variants that can update the external influence and uncertainty [15], overcoming the problem of insufficient a priori knowledge, or weighting the observation by the inverse of the variance [16], an approach that led to an increase in the accuracy.

The aforementioned smoothing techniques are generally applied on all observations and hence tend to correct and modify also true observations, resulting so possibly in a heavily modified series.

2.3.2 Data driven techniques

An alternative solution, made possible by the increasing collection of data, is to exploit past observations to correct the current ones. Variants of this approach, applied to GPS trajectories, include the extraction of main routes, using densities, and the creation of safe areas (circled areas centred to each main route's point), used then to correct the points falling into it [4].

A different technique [17] employs data to detect close sub-trajectories, based on the distance of their characteristics, marking a trajectory as outlying if at least a certain number of sub-trajectories were marked as "not close".

Moreover, when considering specifically GPS trajectories, some studies adopted pre-determined trajectories, known a priori, to correct the readings, obtained from a GPS sensor, while following a certain route [5].

Previously mentioned approaches are based on data related to the same region/route or similar trajectories. However, when considering sport activities performed outdoors, these can vary heavily in terms of movements based on the type of activity and environment. Moreover, the absence of data, related to the same activity and in the correspondent area, would prevent or obstacle the application of the aforementioned methods.

2.3.3 Constraint based techniques

These techniques are generally based on order or sequential relations, so relations that should hold over time and that can be used to detect inconsistencies. Similarly, speed constraints can be used to identify outliers [6].

However, the definition of the constraints or relations is possible only in activities where constraints actually exist, for example for vehicles following a road, while their identification on more dynamic activities, such as sport ones, could be more problematic.

2.3.4 Statistics based techniques

This category comprises techniques which include Markov Models, therefore processes defining the transition from a certain state to another. Markov processes can so be used to predict the values

of a time series, using then the comparison between them and the actual observations as a cleaning strategy [6].

Furthermore, dynamic probabilistic models, such as Spatio-Temporal Probabilistic Models (STPM), can be used to model the relationships between the available attributes using conditional probabilities, calculating so the probability of the observation and applying a threshold based cleaning [6].

A statistical approach more specific to the problem of cleaning GPS data [18] modelled the change of speed between two consecutive points, following the idea that this value should be more constrained. The cleaning problem can then be modelled as the search of the sequence of points with the largest likelihood. Clearly, the repaired sequence should be close to the original one, so the repairing cost is also considered, when evaluating candidates.

2.3.5 Anomaly detection techniques

Another approach, employed to clean time series, is the detection of anomalies. Generally, this is performed predicting first the next observation and applying then a threshold. Methods to predict the next point include the previously mentioned AR and ARIMA models [6].

An alternative approach [19] consists in partitioning the original trajectories in multiple sub-trajectories, dividing it at so-called "characteristic points" [19], namely points, identified using a threshold determined through an ad-hoc analysis, where the direction or speed changes significantly. After that, a consistency model, using Random Sample Consensus, was built for each sub-trajectory, identifying so the local anomalous points. However, in the case of certain trajectories, such as those collected when performing sport activities, it would be challenging to determine the appropriate threshold values that could be used for the partitioning phase.

Furthermore, a two-step cleaning approach was proposed [20]. In the first phase, a threshold on the reachability speed between points was used to remove outliers, with then the application of the underlying map to snap the points to their actual position.

Lastly, a similar approach [9], which was also based on prior knowledge and thresholds, removed first points with an altitude outside the known range in the considered region, applying then a second threshold on the distance between two consecutive points and a Gaussian Kernel smoothing on the resulting points.

The preceding approaches, based on the thresholds, can be challenging to adopt when applying it on traces recorded while performing quite dynamic and diverse activities, such as sport activities.

2.3.6 Machine learning techniques

Alternatively, machine learning techniques can be applied, for example employing the DBSCAN clustering algorithm to merge directly reachable cluster of points, or GANs and LSTM models to perform anomaly detection [6].

Furthermore, decision trees and SVM were chained with the goal of classifying GPS points, collected by a truck company using their employees' smartphones, in three different categories: invalid data (points far from the possible routes), weak data (exceeding a certain threshold on speed or acceleration) and normal data [7]. In particular, decision trees were used to distinguish invalid data, with SVM being responsible for the detection of weak data. The overall process showed a good result in terms of accuracy [7].

Moreover, neural networks have also been applied to predict, for example, the destination of a taxi trip [8]. However, in the reported case, a mean shift algorithm was first applied on the destination of the training trajectories, obtaining so a set of possible destination clusters. The neural network was then used to predict the probabilities of the test trajectory segment to end at each cluster and the

final prediction was a weighted average of the cluster centres, with the weights being represented by the predicted probabilities.

An alternative approach, that incorporates a machine learning technique, was proposed in [21]. Their approach is based on the idea that an automatic repairing system for GPS trajectories should take into account the speed change, the travel distance and also the repairing distance. For each point, the proposed method considers a circle centred at the point, which is then divided in a set of grid cells, based on a width parameter. Each point at the intersection of the cells, including the original observation, is considered as a possible candidate for the correction. For each candidate, an overall score, taking into account the distances mentioned before and the speed change, is computed. The goal of the procedure is to find the sequences that minimised the overall score (the sum of the scores of the single points). However, the authors decided to "personalise" the radius of the circle considered for each point, training a regression model on points collected using the Android API, which returns also the error radius. An unbiased estimation of the variance was added to the value outputted by the regression, and the obtained value was used in the cleaning procedure. A comparison between SVM and Random Forests showed how the latter approach achieved better results.

Chapter 3

Annotation App

3.1 Motivation

At the beginning of the project, researches were undertaken in order to obtain a dataset containing annotated GPS traces, therefore traces where the errors have been highlighted. However, the researches showed how, although many datasets containing GPS traces are available, annotations for errors are generally not included.

For this reason, a web platform, where users can upload their GPS traces, annotating then the various considered errors, was developed from scratch and used to obtain the required dataset, based on the specifications obtained from the requirements' analysis outlined in appendix A.

3.2 System's description

The "Track Annotation" web platform ¹ was developed using HTML, CSS and JavaScript (jQuery² and NodeJS³). The result of the development is an application that allows any user to upload a file representing a GPS trace. The input file can be provided in the widely adopted GPX, GeoJSON or KML formats and, in order to be considered valid, it should comprise both GPS data (represented as points) and associated timestamps. When a new trace is uploaded, it is processed on-device by the application. The GPS data are parsed, in order to identify the recorded data and recognise if they already contain annotations, which are in this case loaded. After that, the non-overlapping GPS points are displayed to the user as a sequence of points connected by a line. Two points are considered as overlapping if their distance, as the crow flies, is below 1 meter. This filter was necessary because the detected points will appear as overlapped on the 2D map, resulting in a more difficult annotation process and noise in the data. Moreover, a previous test on points belonging to 150 running and walking traces denoted how nearly 14% of them are actually overlapped[22]. The distance calculated to detect such points does not include altitude, given that the trace is displayed on a 2D map, and this would prevent users to easily distinguish two overlapped points which are different only in terms of altitude.

Moreover, a plot of the altitude data, for each displayed point, is available in the bottom-right section of the application, providing additional information that could be useful during the annotation process.

¹<https://api.dawnets.unibz.it/>

²<https://jquery.com/>

³<https://nodejs.org/it/>

The user can then select any point as annotated, dragging then the start and end markers of the annotation to resize it. Alternatively, an annotation can be resized using also the point indexes and the two associated controls. Moreover, the annotation bar allows the user to select the type of the annotation, among the following possibilities:

- Pause: when the selected movements were a pause and are the result of GPS reception errors.
- Outlier: when the point, due to a reception error, is in an incorrect position.
- Indoor: a point collected while being indoor in a building or tunnel
- Unknown: when the point is in an incorrect position but does not belong to the previous categories.
- Correct: annotation used to explicitly mark a segment as fully correct. Correct segments are then used in the preparation of the training set as positive examples.

Figure 3.1: An example of an annotation on a loaded GPS trace. The annotation can be resized using the two markers or the associated indexes in the annotation bar. The possibility to change the type of annotation is also provided.

When the user completes the annotations, he/she can submit the annotated trace to our server in order to include it in the dataset. During the submission process, the possibility of providing some additional information, such as a nickname to identify the user, the device used to record the trace and the type of activity, is provided.

Moreover, users are offered the possibility to download the annotated version of the trace in the GeoJSON format, for offline reference.

When an annotated trace is submitted, it is anonymously uploaded to our system, as explained more in details in the following technical implementation section. After a trace is submitted, it is still possible to access and modify it through the direct URL provided when the process is completed successfully.

3.3 System's technical implementation

The technologies used to implement the track annotation system, as mentioned in the previous section, are HTML, CSS and JavaScript (jQuery and NodeJS).

The web interface of the application was written in HTML and CSS, using Bootstrap 4.5.3⁴ to obtain a responsive layout and exploit some already available components.

⁴<https://getbootstrap.com/docs/4.5/getting-started/introduction/>

The GPS trace selected by the user is loaded and parsed using Leaflet-FileLayer⁵, to obtain a consistent GeoJSON representation starting from different formats (GPX, KML and GeoJSON).

The annotation functionality was developed using JavaScript and jQuery, using Leaflet.js⁶ to display a map over which the trace is drawn and Plotly⁷ to draw the altitude plot. The code that allows the user to annotate a certain segment of the trace was developed entirely from scratch using jQuery, incorporating also a customised version of the Leaflet.AlmostOver⁸ plugin to simplify the selection of the various points, allowing the user to select a point by clicking near to it and not enforcing an exact click on it.

As mentioned in section 3.2, it was necessary to remove overlapped points, since their presence could have complicated the annotation process for the user, making indistinguishable points different only in terms of altitude. For this reason, a custom function eliminates a point if this is at less than 1m than the previous one, "adjusting" then the position of the previous point averaging the features of the two. Note how an adjusted point is then never taken as basis for the distance computation to the next one, avoiding so to collapse a subsequent point that was originally at more than the specified distance from the previous one, limiting so the modifications to the input trace.

When a user has annotated all the necessary segments, he/she can submit the trace to the system, using the associated button and form, providing also additional information. When submitting the annotated trace, the application uses jQuery to perform an authenticated POST request to a custom public NodeJS API, hosted by the same NodeJS server instance that serves the Track Annotation app. The API will then insert, or update, in case of a change to an already submitted trace, the given document into a NoSQL database hosted using MongoDB⁹. The deployment of the two server instances, namely NodeJS and MongoDB, was performed using Kubernetes¹⁰ on a cluster made available by the Free University of Bolzano.

The use of NoSQL technologies for data storage was chosen because, in our specific case, each trace is represented by an entire GeoJSON document and thus more difficulties could have been encountered when storing it using a table of a relational database. Moreover, NoSQL databases are increasing support to geospatial data which, along with their scalability advantages, results in a technology suitable for our specific use case [23].

Furthermore, the document model seems to combine generally good performances and geospatial functionalities [23]. MongoDB, one of the alternatives proposed by [23], offers the possibility to use a document model with support to geospatial data, also in the free Community Server version. For this reason, it was chosen as data storage solution for this project.

When the trace is inserted or updated in MongoDB, the API returns the unique ID of the inserted document, which is then used, by the Track Annotation app, to generate a unique URL that is shown to the user and that can be used to access the trace subsequently, for later changes.

For more details, the source code of the application can be consulted at [24].

3.4 The obtained dataset

In a five-month period, we collected 61 traces from various users and related to various outdoor activities. The majority of the tracks (93%) was collected in the Trentino-South Tyrol region and, more in general, they were all collected in the northern regions of Italy. Table 3.1 summarises the activities that were recorded and uploaded in the dataset:

⁵<https://github.com/makinacorp/Leaflet.FileLayer>

⁶<https://leafletjs.com/>

⁷<https://plotly.com/>

⁸<https://github.com/makinacorp/Leaflet.AlmostOver>

⁹<https://www.mongodb.com/it-it>

¹⁰<https://kubernetes.io/it/>

Activity type	Number of traces
Hiking	24
Walking	14
Ski Mountaineering	11
Cycling	6
Mountain Biking	3
Running	2
Sailing	1

Table 3.1: Activities recorded and uploaded in the dataset

As can be seen, although most of the activities present in the dataset are related with walking and hiking, there is a satisfying variety of less common activities, such as ski mountaineering, mountain biking and a quite rare sailing activity.

When analysing the points present in the dataset and how they were annotated, we observed how, out of the overall 232, 238 collected points, 13, 514 of them were annotated (corresponding to about 5.82% of the points). This can be explained by the time-consuming annotation process. Figure 3.2 reports a characterisation of the available annotations, revealing how most of the annotated points were explicitly marked as correct, a situation that, in our view, matches the reality since, except in particularly difficult conditions, most of the recorded points will be correct.

Pauses can then be identified as the primary source of errors, along with outliers, with indoor points being rarely annotated.

Figure 3.2: Characterisation of the points present in the dataset

Chapter 4

Modelling

4.1 Data preprocessing

After obtaining the dataset using the Track Annotation app, this was exported from MongoDB as a JSON file and pre-processed, as explained in the following sections.

Moreover, it was chosen not to include in the data, used for the modelling phase, the metadata of the traces, such as the type of activity undertaken, the device used to record it and geographical data related to where the trace was collected. This decision was taken in order to obtain a general model that can be applied on any type of traces.

4.1.1 Coordinate reference system and deltas

When preparing the data for the modelling activity, we decided to focus on the differences between each pair of points of a GPS trace, named deltas, instead of using the positions of the points themselves. This allows the extraction of the movements characteristics of the activities, making so possible to recognise similar patterns recorded in traces located in different parts of the world.

Clearly, the coordinates of each point of the various traces are originally reported according to the geodetic reference system, namely by the following three components: latitude, longitude and altitude. However, these components constitute the coordinates on the geoid representing the earth and are not Cartesian coordinates. Thus, having non-parallel longitude lines, the concept of distance between points is less intuitive than in other coordinate reference systems, complicating so the calculation of the deltas.

For this reason, we decided to convert the initial geodetic coordinates to Earth-Centred Earth-Fixed (ECEF) Cartesian coordinates. In the ECEF coordinate system, the reference is the centre of the earth, represented by the $(0, 0, 0)$ point. The X-axis passes through the Equator and Prime Meridian, with the z-axis passing through the North Pole and the y-axis being orthogonal with respect to the first two axes, as shown in figure 4.1 [25].

The conversion, applied to each point of each trace, was performed using Python and the Pyproj library, which enables transformation between different coordinate reference systems. The result of the conversion is a triplet (x, y, z) that is used, substituting so the original geographic coordinates, for the calculation of the delta between a point and the previous one, generating so the new features.

In case a point does not have an associated altitude, an effect that is possible in certain cases due to a missing measurement by the barometer, it is excluded from the trace and the aforementioned process is performed on the remaining points.

Figure 4.1: Visualisation of ECEF coordinates

4.1.2 Sliding window approach on segments

The second pre-processing activity that was applied is related to the sliding window approach and comprises also the balancing of the dataset.

Firstly, it should be noted how, at this stage, we decided to treat points annotated as "unknown" as not annotated points. This decision arose after concluding that there are insufficient information to consider them as either correct or incorrect, and hence were treated as if they were not evaluated.

After that, we can analyse how, the reasons and intuitions behind the segmentation approach through a sliding window method, reside behind the idea that it would be easier for the model to evaluate a restrained set of points in order to identify errors, instead of the entire trace. A potentially simple solution could be implemented, creating separated fixed-length segments from the original trace. However, the division in separated windows could perhaps "cut" an annotation in various parts, potentially leading so to a more difficult recognition process, as shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Example of how windowing could "cut" an annotation (reported in red)

Following this intuition, we decided to process each trace following a sliding window approach, creating partially overlapping segments, recording their labels and original point indexes, as shown in figure 4.3. The size of the window and the sliding step can be defined using two associated parameters.

The aforementioned process is then repeated on the entire trace and leads to the creation of the segments used as basis of the training set.

The sliding window function does not apply any padding when it comes to the first segment of the trace, with it therefore starting from the first recorded point. However, when reaching the final part of the trace, padding is applied using the maximum value of an integer available in Python, in order to still exploit the possibility of evaluating different segments. This decision was taken

Figure 4.3: Example of sliding windows of size 3 and step 1 and how they can capture more precisely relations between points

following the idea that initially there is no possibility to employ previous data, a condition that results in an additional obstacle when it comes to understand the relation of the first few points, and hence padding the first segments would not be beneficial. The padded values are then not considered during the training of the machine learning model and are so ignored, as explained in the associated later section.

4.2 Choosing LSTM: model comparison

Before committing to a specific machine learning architecture, a comparison between different architectures was performed in order to understand their ability to model location data. For this reason, we decided to test various architectures on a simple activity recognition task, namely the identification of the type of sport activity recorded.

Given the unavailability of the collected dataset at this stage, since the collection process was ongoing, we collected, from publicly available data sources, 75 traces of walking and hiking activities along with 75 traces of running activities.

Three different architectures were tested on a preprocessed version of the dataset, with the goal of distinguishing the segments extracted from traces recorded while performing the two considered activities. In all three tested architectures, a Masking layer has been applied initially to ignore the points resulting from the application of the padding procedure, outlined previously.

According to us, a recurrent approach, based on the widely adopted LSTM architecture, could suit well the considered scenario. However, to validate this hypothesis, we compared a simple LSTM architecture with two different widely adopted architectures: a standard one layer neural network (MLP) to test a general machine learning approach and a convolutional architecture, to experiment the feature extraction capabilities of convolutional approaches.

The tested architectures, illustrated in Figure 4.4, can be characterised more in details as follows:

- An LSTM architecture, composed by 10 hidden units in a single layer
- A neural network composed by a single hidden layer with 10 neurons with relu as activation function
- A convolutional approach composed of a block of 1-dimensional convolution (padding set as same and kernel size to 7), followed by a max pooling layer. This block is used two times, the first with a filter of size 64, while the second one with a 128 sized filter. The convolutional part is then chained with the neural network described above.

The various architectures were implemented using the Keras¹ API of the TensorFlow² package.

¹<https://www.tensorflow.org/guide/keras/>

²<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

Figure 4.4: Representation of the three different architectures tested as first experiment

The result of the classification with the different models, reported in figure 4.5, showed a high accuracy in all three cases, with the LSTM approach showing a reduced variability in the results and being so chosen for further optimisation.

Figure 4.5: Results of the comparison of the three architectures on the 150 traces dataset

4.3 LSTM Architectures comparison

The preliminary experiments, reported in section 4.2, outlined how LSTM outperformed MLP and a convolutional based model, when dealing with GPS data.

For this reason, we decided to investigate further the architecture of the LSTM model, comparing a custom architecture with a vanilla approach and an architecture described in the literature and applied to a similar problem.

The comparison was performed on a dataset composed by the first 42 collected traces, due to time and resources constraints. The dataset, composed by 155,917 points, revealed to have a similar distribution to the final dataset, outlined in the previous chapter, both in terms of activity types and annotations.

4.3.1 Description of the considered architectures

This section briefly describes and illustrates the four various architectures that were used in the aforementioned comparison, while the following section will outline the obtained results.

Custom Architecture

The custom LSTM architecture was selected experimentally with the goal of understanding the non-linear temporal relations between the data in the first layers (in a bidirectional way), reducing then gradually the number of neurons to reach the target output number. It is composed by three layers of LSTM Bidirectional cells, with respectively 100, 100 and 70 cells, followed by a deep neural network composed of three dense fully connected layers with 70, 40 and 5 cells. A dropout rate of 15% was introduced between the LSTM and dense part, as well as between the first two dense layers, as represented in figure 4.6. The output layer, common to all four architectures, is composed by 3 time distributed units, representing the three possible classes, activated using softmax.

Figure 4.6: Visualisation of the custom architecture, part of the comparison among various LSTM architectures

Vanilla Architecture

The second considered architecture is a standard vanilla architecture. Vanilla architectures, initially proposed by Graves and Schmidhuber [26], are the base setup of an LSTM model, since they are composed of a single hidden layer, and are generally taken as reference for comparison with possible variations [27].

In our case, the single hidden LSTM layer, represented also in figure 4.7, contains 150 LSTM cells.

Figure 4.7: Representation of the vanilla architecture, part of the comparison among various LSTM architectures

Driving style analysis architecture

The last considered LSTM architecture was proposed in a study that aimed at classifying the driving style adopted when driving an electric car, starting from GPS data [28]. The classification of various driving styles can be particularly useful with electric cars, since it heavily influences its range.

The authors performed various experiments and found that the best performance could be achieved when analysing acceleration, deceleration and speed when using a Deep LSTM architecture composed of three layers of ten LSTM cells per layer. A resembling architecture, depicted in figure 4.8,

was used in our comparison.

Figure 4.8: Depiction of the driving style analysis architecture, part of the comparison among various LSTM architectures

4.3.2 Evaluating function

Initially, during the training and evaluation of the various model explored in section 4.2, the accuracy was calculated by the framework, both at the end of each epoch and during the evaluation.

However, the creation of the segments, outlined in section 4.1.2, highlighted how most of the points are included in more than one window, as a result of the sliding approach that was adopted.

For this reason, a point to point comparison does not suit perfectly the current outlined scenario, given that a point could be present in more than a window, with its classification being so considered more than one time, compared to the previous model comparison in which each segment obtained a single classification. Furthermore, a point being present in multiple windows could potentially be classified in different ways, depending on the relation with the points included in the specific segment, and considering these multiple classifications will alter the overall result.

The aforementioned reasons hint at the need of a custom evaluation function to calculate accuracy, able to collapse multiple classifications in a single one, without considering the same point multiple times.

The result of the mentioned analysis is an approach that, given a set of segments, correct labels and original indexes, calculates the correct accuracy of the classifications, using only annotated points, included those annotated as correct, specified using their IDs. In this way, the reported accuracy is calculated only on the points for which a classification was explicitly enforced by the user, and does not consider points that, due to their location or characteristics, may not have been analysed carefully and for which no certain classification was given.

The core idea behind the custom implemented evaluation function is to accumulate the various classifications, for each annotated point, in a Python dictionary containing, for every point, an integer counter for each available class. Whenever a segment is classified, the original indexes of the points are retrieved from the indices array generated during the segments' creation, with the function increasing the counter corresponding to the predicted class of each annotated point. When all segments are classified, it applies then, to each point in the dictionary, majority voting to classify it. The aforementioned process can be summarised with the pseudocode reported in Algorithm 1.

Moreover, in order to simplify the comparison with the correct labels, points, both in the predicted and ground truth arrays, are sorted by their indexes. The final step, after obtaining the two sorted arrays, is to compare the predictions with the ground truth values and calculate so the overall accuracy, a process undertaken using the available Sklearn function.

Furthermore, a confusion matrix, reporting the errors and correct predictions for each different class, is reported also using Sklearn³, for the calculation, and Seaborn⁴, for the visualisation.

³<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

⁴<https://seaborn.pydata.org/>

Algorithm 1 Compress points predictions

```

1: procedure COMPRESSPOINTS PREDICTIONS(predictions, indices, nClasses)
2:   points  $\leftarrow$  dictionary()
3:   uniqueIndices  $\leftarrow$  indices.unique()
4:   for index  $\in$  uniqueIndices do                                 $\triangleright$  initialise for each point a counter per class
5:     points[index]  $\leftarrow$  [0, 0, ..., nClasses]
6:   end for
7:   for predictedWindow  $\in$  predictions do                         $\triangleright$  count the various predictions of each point
8:     for predictedPoint  $\in$  predictedWindow do
9:       pointIndex  $\leftarrow$  predictedPoint.index                     $\triangleright$  get point index
10:      pointClass  $\leftarrow$  predictedPoint.predictedClass           $\triangleright$  get point predicted class
11:      points[pointIndex][pointClass] += 1                         $\triangleright$  increase point's counter for that class
12:    end for
13:  end for
14:  for point  $\in$  points do                                         $\triangleright$  get class with more votes for each point
15:    points[point]  $\leftarrow$  maxIndex(point)
16:  end for
17:  return points
18: end procedure

```

4.3.3 Architectures' evaluation procedure

In order to evaluate each architecture, the following procedure was followed. First, it was chosen to conduct a grid search on a subset of the dataset, given the large amount of time necessary to investigate each combination of the investigated parameters. For this reason, the search was performed using the first 42 collected traces, as mentioned in the previous section.

Moreover, after a careful analysis of the parameters and their role in the training of the model, we decided to focus our attention on three parameters:

- Window size: namely the window size used to generate the segments from each trace
- Step size: therefore the step or "jump" performed by the segments generating function between the start of two consecutive segments
- Epochs: the epochs for which the model is trained

The combinations of the different parameters were extracted according to the candidate values reported in table 4.1.

Window size	3, 5, 10, 15
Step size	1, 2, 3, 5
Epochs	10, 20, 30, 40, 50

Table 4.1: Table describing the candidate values investigated for each parameter.

Each combination has then been tested by following the subsequent procedure, starting from the same training set:

1. The segments are generated using the sliding window approach and the parameters specified by the current combination

2. A KFold object is created with the number of folds set to three
3. The KFold split is performed on the set of annotated points, leading so to the definition of two sets containing the IDs of only annotated points.
4. Each generated segment is analysed and the intersections of the indexes of its points with the extracted training IDs and test IDs, as well as with the current content of the two sets are computed, leading us to one of the following possibilities:
 - (a) A segment that contains at least a point with an ID extracted to be in the training set, and it does not contain any point that was already added in the test set. In this case, the segment is added to the training set.
 - (b) A segment that contains at least a point with an ID extracted to be in the test set, and it does not contain any point that was already added in the training set. In this case, the segment is added to the test set.
 - (c) A segment that contains a point with an ID extracted to be in the train/test set, but also contains a point from the other set. In this case, the segment is ignored.

Regardless from the set in which each annotated segment is assigned to, not annotated points are treated as correct points.

5. The chosen model is then trained, for each fold, on the generated training set and evaluated on the test set, obtaining an accuracy value
6. The average of the accuracies of the various folds is considered as the accuracy of the evaluated model

4.3.4 Results of the comparison

This section presents the results of the outlined comparison, in terms of accuracy of each tested model. Table 4.2 presents the three best combinations for each tested model.

Architecture	Epochs	Window size	Step size	Accuracy
Custom LSTM	30	15	2	0.864243
	40	15	2	0.849197
	20	15	2	0.848749
Vanilla LSTM	40	15	2	0.860122
	10	15	2	0.859688
	50	15	5	0.853060
Driving LSTM	40	15	2	0.833365
	20	15	2	0.820335
	30	15	2	0.818517

Table 4.2: Table representing the three best combinations per model

From the above results, we can extract the following three best combinations overall, summarised for clarity in table 4.3

In general, analysing the two reported tables, we can see how the difference between the models in terms of accuracy is not particularly relevant.

However, we can notice how most of the reported combinations agree on two parameters, namely the window and step size.

Epochs	Window size	Step size	Accuracy	Architecture
30	15	2	0.864243	Custom LSTM
40	15	2	0.860122	Vanilla LSTM
10	15	2	0.859688	Vanilla LSTM

Table 4.3: Best three combinations overall

Although the difference in terms of accuracy is relative modest, we decided to adopt the winning model and therefore to employ the **custom architecture** on segments of size **15**, generated by applying the sliding window approach with a step of **2**, training then the model for **30** epochs.

4.4 Final model and evaluation

After performing the grid search on a subset of 42 traces, applying a 3-fold validation splitting the annotated points, we were ready to test the best combination, resulting from the grid search, on the entire dataset.

4.4.1 Folding on traces

Moreover, applying the model on the entire dataset, having thus more data, allowed us to apply a split on the traces instead of using single annotated points. For this reason, the process, although following closely the one described in section 4.3.3, performs a 3-fold split on the traces, obtaining so a set of traces for the train set and one for the test set. Among the traces present in each set, the criteria outlined previously and used to balance the sets is still applied: for each segment belonging to a trace, this is considered only if it contains at least an annotated point, with not annotated points being treated as correct points, as outlined in the original description of the criteria in section 4.3.3.

4.4.2 TensorFlow Lite model: enabling mobile deployment

As mentioned in section 4.2, the various architectures, adopted in this project, were implemented using the Keras API available in the TensorFlow package. However, this would mean that in order to run the trained model, the entire TensorFlow package will be required.

However, this dependency constraint will contrast with one of our goals, namely the possibility to run the model also on portable devices, such as smartphones or smartwatches, allowing various mobile scenarios to be considered.

Furthermore, we can also notice that not all functionalities made available by the complete TensorFlow package are needed after the training, since only the running capabilities are necessary.

For this reason, we decided to convert the model, at each fold, to a TensorFlow Lite model⁵, thus a model optimised for run-time which only needs a specific component, derived from the TensorFlow standard package, as a dependency. The conversion of the model is needed in order to make it compatible with the operators available in the reduced runtime dependency. The conversion of the model strictly followed the one outlined by the official documentation⁶ and was performed without specific optimizations, to ensure the preservation of the predicting capabilities while still obtaining lighter dependencies.

⁵<https://www.tensorflow.org/lite>

⁶<https://www.tensorflow.org/lite/convert/rnn>

Following this idea, the model, after having trained on each fold using TensorFlow standard package, was then converted to a TensorFlow Lite model and run on the same test data of the given fold, to verify its predicting capabilities.

4.4.3 Model evaluation: the complete process

After the aforementioned additions to the training and evaluation process, this can so be summarised as follows:

1. The chosen architecture, namely the custom one, was evaluated using a 3-fold validation division on the 61 available traces, considering then, for each trace, only segments which contain at least an annotated point
2. For each of the three folds, the evaluation process was the following:
 - (a) The model was trained, using the complete TensorFlow package on two-thirds of the available dataset
 - (b) Its predicting performance were evaluated on the remaining third of data
 - (c) The model was converted to a TensorFlow Lite model, following the procedure outlined in the previous section
 - (d) The TensorFlow Lite model was evaluated on the same remaining third of data
3. After the 3-fold evaluation, the model is trained on the entire training set and then converted to a TensorFlow Lite model

4.4.4 The results

The results of the evaluation of the model on the complete dataset, applying the aforementioned method, are shown in table 4.4.

Firstly, we can notice how we reported only a single value of accuracy and confusion matrix for each fold, although two models were tested at each round: the standard TensorFlow model and the TensorFlow Lite model. This happens because we could ascertain how the conversion without optimisation does not affect the model weights and therefore the accuracy, with the two models realising the same results.

The model, in our opinion, showed a really good performance overall, with a perfect score in the recognition of correct points in all three folds. Pauses are also generally well recognised, an important result considering how this annotation was the leading one between the various errors in the collected dataset. Outlier and indoor points recognition was satisfying, although their rarity in the dataset with respect to the two other annotations may have impacted the accuracy of their identification, leaving space for improvements.

Fold	Accuracy	Confusion matrix																														
Fold 1	0.9856	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>True Correct</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Pause</td> <td>0.03</td> <td>0.97</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Outlier</td> <td>0.07</td> <td>0.02</td> <td>0.91</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Indoor</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>1.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Correct</td> <td>Pause</td> <td>Outlier</td> <td>Indoor</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td colspan="4">Predicted</td> </tr> </table>	True Correct	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	True Pause	0.03	0.97	0.00	0.00	True Outlier	0.07	0.02	0.91	0.00	True Indoor	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00		Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor		Predicted			
True Correct	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00																												
True Pause	0.03	0.97	0.00	0.00																												
True Outlier	0.07	0.02	0.91	0.00																												
True Indoor	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00																												
	Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor																												
	Predicted																															
Fold 2	0.9662	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>True Correct</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Pause</td> <td>0.15</td> <td>0.79</td> <td>0.06</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Outlier</td> <td>0.12</td> <td>0.01</td> <td>0.86</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Indoor</td> <td>0.36</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.64</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Correct</td> <td>Pause</td> <td>Outlier</td> <td>Indoor</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td colspan="4">Predicted</td> </tr> </table>	True Correct	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	True Pause	0.15	0.79	0.06	0.00	True Outlier	0.12	0.01	0.86	0.00	True Indoor	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.64		Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor		Predicted			
True Correct	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00																												
True Pause	0.15	0.79	0.06	0.00																												
True Outlier	0.12	0.01	0.86	0.00																												
True Indoor	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.64																												
	Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor																												
	Predicted																															
Fold 3	0.9649	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>True Correct</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Pause</td> <td>0.06</td> <td>0.94</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Outlier</td> <td>0.21</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.78</td> <td>0.01</td> </tr> <tr> <td>True Indoor</td> <td>0.20</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.00</td> <td>0.80</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Correct</td> <td>Pause</td> <td>Outlier</td> <td>Indoor</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td colspan="4">Predicted</td> </tr> </table>	True Correct	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	True Pause	0.06	0.94	0.00	0.00	True Outlier	0.21	0.00	0.78	0.01	True Indoor	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.80		Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor		Predicted			
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True Indoor	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.80																												
	Correct	Pause	Outlier	Indoor																												
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Table 4.4: Evaluation on the entire dataset, splitting on the traces

Chapter 5

Correcting errors

While the previous chapter concentrated on the detection of errors, this section explores different techniques that can be used in order to correct points detected as incorrect.

5.1 A special type of error: pauses

Firstly, it should be noted how one of the considered error categories, namely pauses, differs from the others, when it comes to correction.

In fact, points representing pauses should appear, in the ideal case, stacked one upon the other, given that the position of the receiver did not change in the considered time frame. However, often pauses are represented, in the GPS trace, by a cloud of points resulting from a measurement error by the GPS sensor.

For the aforementioned reasons, points identified by the model as belonging to a pause can be directly removed, resulting so in a more smoothed trace with no unnecessary points.

5.2 Correcting misplaced points: techniques

Pauses, as explained in the previous section, can be directly removed, a step that can not be performed on misplaced points, which need then to be corrected. This section presents various techniques that can be used in order to adjust the position of misplaced points, and that were tested and compared.

Unfortunately, in this case, no quantitative analysis could be performed, since it would require also a set of ground truth traces for each of the considered ones. However, we compared the various techniques by applying them on randomly selected traces, trying to cover a wide range of cases, inspecting then the results visually in order to determine the impact of the correction.

This section presents some examples of how the various techniques modify the original traces and describes the reasons that brought us to the selection of a certain approach.

5.2.1 Cubic spline interpolation

The first technique, considered as a baseline, is an interpolation based technique. More in general, interpolation is the process of "connecting points", namely the estimation of some unknown points based on the available ones. Various interpolations can be applied, ranging from the more intuitive linear interpolation, which connects the known points using a straight line, to more refined versions

that increment the degree of the polynomial used to represent the data, such as, for example, the cubic spline interpolation.

The cubic spline interpolation fits a cubic polynomial to each pair of points, choosing then the values of the two remaining free parameters in such a way that the resulting shape agrees, in terms of curvature and direction, to the adjacent ones at the endpoints [29].

Clearly, interpolation should be applied only on points whose value is unknown or incorrect. For this reason, we decided first to apply the final model, designed and trained as outlined in section 4.4. The original GPS trace was so pre-processed to convert the coordinates to ECEF and the sliding window approach was applied to obtain the segments needed by the model. After applying the model, the predictions were compressed, for each point, by applying majority voting, as mentioned in the previous chapter.

Subsequently, the values of the coordinates of the points predicted as misplaced are then set as unknown and the aforementioned process, implemented inside the correction module using the SciPy spline interpolation with the chosen order, is applied to derive the coordinates of the interpolated points.

In our case, we decided to test the outlined technique with three different orders: 2, 3 and 4. The interpolation technique was applied on various traces, only on the points marked as outliers. Figure 5.1 reports an example of the same outlying area corrected with the considered spline orders.

Figure 5.1: Spline correction on outliers with different orders. In yellow outliers on the original trace, in red the interpolated points.

The interpolations reported in the figure show how this technique does not suit a correcting scenario, since they tend to ignore the general context and the resulting curve could heavily differ in terms of shape from the desired one.

5.2.2 Kalman filters

Kalman filters, as mentioned in the in section 2.3, are one of the most employed techniques, when it comes to the correction of data coming from sensors.

The structure of a Kalman filter comprises the state vector, which represents the state variables that are used, both observed and hidden variables. In our case, the observed variable are the three components identifying a position, namely latitude, longitude and altitude, converted in the ECEF coordinates x, y, z . Hidden variables can be used to incorporate some extra information, useful for making the prediction. In case of positions and movements, the velocity in each direction is often used as hidden variable, approached we decided to follow and that leads to three observed variable and three hidden ones [30], as can be seen in figure 5.2.

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ \dot{x} \\ y \\ \dot{y} \\ z \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.2: Representation of the state matrix, with x , y and z being the true coordinates, while the dotted symbols represent the correspondent velocities

The second component of a Kalman filter is the state transition matrix, which relates how the prediction of each of the observed components depends on the variables present in the state vector. For example, in our case, we consider the position on the x axis to be dependent on the previous position (so x itself) and on the velocity (\dot{x}) and time that passed from the previous measurement (Δt). In order to express this dependency, We can so write the following transition equation:

$$x = 1x + \Delta t\dot{x} + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 \quad (5.2)$$

Analysing the velocity, given that we do not have any data related to acceleration and deceleration, we assume it to be independent of other variables.

A similar approach can be applied on the remaining state variables, which all depend on the previous value, velocity and time. This brings us to the definition of a state transition matrix, which contains the coefficients of the transition equations defined for each variable, as shown in figure 5.3.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta t & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5.3: State transition matrix for our Kalman Filter

Moreover, we specified the measurement matrix, which identifies which variables are the observed ones and which are not. In our case, clearly, the observed variables are represented by x , y , z since we do not measure velocity explicitly.

Furthermore, the prediction noise that is applied in the process was defined to be white noise, following the general accepted approach[31].

The last parameter that needs to be specified is the measurement uncertainty/noise, and it was set to be $4.9m$, the average accuracy reported when it come to the GPS, as outlined in section 2.1.

The filter can then be used to obtain a prediction, which can then be updated using the measurements obtained by the GPS sensor and a factor called *Kalman Gain*. The Kalman Gain parameter models how the prediction and measurement should be combined, based on the confidence it has in the measurement, given its likelihood, in order to minimise the error of their combination.

The aforementioned Kalman Filter was implemented using the Filterpy¹ Python library, specifying the aforementioned vectors and matrices as parameters.

After the filter initialisation, each point is processed and the Δt parameter is calculated based on the obtained timestamp. Its value is then updated in the state-transition matrix accordingly, obtaining so a more accurate prediction of the position, by using the associated method of Filterpy. The

¹<https://github.com/rlabbe/filterpy>

prediction of the Kalman filter is the updated using the measurement and the *update* function of Filterpy, obtaining so a refined estimate that replaces the measured position in the GPS trace.

In our case, in order to respect the original implementation, we applied the filter on the entire trace. Figure 5.4 reports the result of the filter's application on the example trace.

Figure 5.4: Kalman's correction on the entire example trace. Yellow points represent outliers on the original trace.

Clearly, as expected, we can observe how also correct points are modified, leading to quite a different trace than the original one. Applying this technique on the entire trace would not exploit the classification provided by the model, and this reason brought us to the first of the Kalman filter's variants we analysed: Kalman filters on outliers.

5.2.3 Kalman filters on outliers

The Kalman filter standard approach, outlined in the previous section, showed how it could potentially modify also points registered as correct, introducing an additional error.

For this reason, we decided to propose a Kalman filter that exploits the model and focused the correction only on the points predicted as outliers.

Thereby, we implemented, in the correction module, a Kalman filtering function which, given the points and the predictions obtained by the model, processes each point, as performed also in the original Kalman Filter, and, based on the prediction, replaces the point with the refined estimate of the Kalman Filter, if the point is predicted as outlier, or keeps the original measured position, if the prediction characterises the point as correct. Moreover, when a correct point is encountered, the refined prediction of the Kalman filter is replaced with the correct measured position, ensuring that the next prediction will be based on the correct points and will not accumulate errors.

In this way, the Kalman Filter can still learn its parameters, such as the Kalman Gain, but the position is reset whenever a correct position is encountered.

Figure 5.5 shows the modifications of the Kalman filter only on the points belonging to the outlying area.

It is possible to observe how, this time, only the yellow points, representing outliers in the original trace, are modified. The modification, however, is still quite important, such as in the case of the curve in segment 1, with the points being "shifted and compressed", while segment 2 reports what can be considered as a smoothed version of the original points.

Figure 5.5: Kalman's correction on outliers only

It is worth noting how, when applying this technique, the state and parameters of the filter are still impacted also by correct points, with their position being then left unmodified by our implementation. However, the filter is not able to understand the difference in the classification of the points it is evaluating, updating always its internal state as if every point requires a correction.

5.2.4 Separate Kalman Filters

The aforementioned reason brought us to the application of a separate Kalman filter for each area containing outliers. This approach does not only prevent the internal state change on correct points, but improves also performances, since a lower number of points is evaluated.

In our implementation, whenever an area containing outliers is encountered, a new Kalman filter is created and is applied on the identified area, using at most the preceding five points in order to acquire some context, as represented also in figure 5.6.

For example, if a point n is an outlier, the filter considers at most also the points $n - 5$ to $n - 1$.

Figure 5.6: Representation of the separate Kalman Filters techniques

As performed also in the previously outlined techniques, the adjusted position outputted by the filter for the preceding correct points is then reset to the recorded position.

In this way, by applying a separate filter for each area containing outliers instead of a single filter on the entire trace, performances are improved by avoiding the prediction and adjustment of the positions of correct points which, being generally present in a larger quantity, could occur frequently in a consecutive way.

Figure 5.7 reports the testing sub-trace corrected with the aforementioned technique.

In this case, we can observe how the correction, although still modifying consistently some points, tends to respect more the original shape of the trajectory, resulting in a more convincing

Figure 5.7: Result of the correction obtained by applying the separate Kalman filters on outliers

correction.

5.2.5 Bidirectional Separate Kalman Filter

A last variation of the Kalman filters we decided to consider was the bidirectional application of separate Kalman filters, outlined in the previous section. The intuition behind this implementation resides in the behaviour adopted generally by Kalman filters, which tend to maintain the previous direction, when correcting future points. However, having the entire trace, we can apply two different separate Kalman filters for each area of outliers: one going "forward" and one "backward", trying so to smooth the possible correction and to exploit all the available information.

Following this idea, a Kalman filter is applied from the first outlying point on-wards, considering at most the preceding 5 points, and one backwards, starting so from the last outlying point in the considered area, while still considering the preceding points (in the opposite direction), to build the context, as represented also in figure 5.8.

Figure 5.8: Representation of the Bidirectional Separate Kalman Filters techniques

The correction that is applied is then the average correction between the ones obtained by the two filters. Figure 5.9 reports the result of the correction on the example area.

Compared to the previous approach, whose results were reported in figure 5.7, the correction obtained by the aforementioned method results in a more smoothed trace with less "peaks" and sudden direction changes.

Figure 5.9: Result of the application of the bidirectional separate Kalman filters correcting technique

5.2.6 Custom delta correction

The last considered corrective approach, also based on the previously obtained model, is a delta correction inspired by the adversarial example generation and attack [32].

In an adversarial attack, posed to a neural network, a certain input X classified as Y is modified to \hat{X} such that \hat{X} is still closed to X , according to a certain distance metrics d , but is misclassified [32]. The goal of the described attack is therefore to slightly modify an example to reach a certain classification, while maintaining its general characteristics. Generally this is achieved by computing the gradient of the current classification of the input X with respect to the desired classification, modifying then the input accordingly towards the target classification but usually "clipping" the modification to avoid radical changes and maintain \hat{X} close to X .

A similar approach was followed in the delta correction proposed to correct outliers in a GPS trace. Given that each point in each segment obtains a classification by the designed model, we would like to modify the points in the segment so that the classification of the segment will result in all points being correct. The modification to each point of the segment, which can be related to all three components x, y, z , was named *delta* and was initially set to 0. Clearly, no modification to the time feature was performed, given that it reflects the sampling time of the device used to record the trace.

We designed so a function which, given a segment, repeats the following steps for a certain number of epochs, in our case 30:

- Sums the current delta (initially 0) to the segment containing the points
- Classifies the segment with the pre-trained model, obtaining a classification Y
- Calculates a loss l between the obtained prediction Y and the desired prediction (all correct points)
- Calculates the gradient of the loss with respect to the current delta
- Applies the calculated gradient to the current delta, using an optimizer (in our case Adam)
- Clips the value of the current optimization to ensure the modification to the point is not dramatic, but allowing a larger modification than those generally applied in adversarial attacks (clip value of 0.1)

- Ensures the modification to the time feature of all points is zero, as well as the delta of the x, y, z features of correct points, since, being correct, they do not need to be modified

At the end of the process, the delta matrix contains a modification to each feature of each incorrect points that leads the classification of the segment towards a correct classification.

The aforementioned procedure is then repeated for each segment. After applying the aforementioned procedure to each segment, the result is a delta correction that could be applied directly to the segment, by simply summing it. However, given that segments were generated using the sliding window approach, a point is generally included in more than one segment and could so receive multiple corrections.

For this reason, we decided to accumulate the deltas of each point, obtained from the previous procedure, computing then the mean of the various obtained corrections. The calculated mean correction is then applied to incorrect points by summing it to the original ECEF coordinates.

Figure 5.10 reports the result of the delta correction on the example trace.

Figure 5.10: Result of the application of the delta correction on the example trace

We can observe how outliers positions are slightly modified, with the goal of obtaining a smoother trajectory. However, the modifications do not result in an important impact on the sub-trace, leading to minor improvements and hence an ineffective correction.

5.2.7 Track Simplification

Various software and applications, which focus on managing GPS tracks, are available online. A wide range of the available applications offers also some track simplification functionalities, such as for example the possibility to remove some points based on certain criteria, or to unify subtracks.

An example of such application is GPS Babel², a free software often used to convert GPS traces between formats. However, its functionalities are not limited only to data conversion, since it offers to its users also some data manipulation features.

The software is available as a command line tool or also by using a GUI which comprises options for the most used filters, although not all of them are accessible by the interface.

In particular, the following options/filters can be applied to correct/clean a GPS trace:

- Remove duplicate points

²<https://www.gpsbabel.org/>

- Remove points outside a certain radius from a fixed location
- Remove points within a certain distance
- Limit the number of points of a certain trace to a given amount. This can be used in order to simplify it and possibly remove errors.
- Remove unreliable points, therefore points with a large dilution of precision (DOP) in either the horizontal axis (HDOP) or vertical axis (VDOP). A threshold value needs to be specified.

A test on some of the available filters was performed by applying the following options:

1. Limiting the trace to a maximum of 1900 points, starting from 2152 points (a reduction of the 11%).
2. Duplicate points were eliminated
3. A minimum distance of 1m between the points was applied

Figure 5.11 reports the example area after the filters have been applied, reporting how, although some points were removed, the resulting sub-trace closely follows the raw one.

Figure 5.11: Result of the application of the filters using GPS Babel

No test related to the VDOP and HDOP filters was performed, given that those values are not reported by most of the portable GPS receivers available in consumer devices such as smartphones and smartwatches.

5.3 The adopted technique: motivations

The previous section outlined the correcting techniques that were considered, with an example of their application on a randomly selected trace. Such a comparison was performed on multiple traces and the results were visually inspected, with the goal of selecting the technique that results in the most effective correction, without distorting dramatically the original trace.

The technique we decided to adopt was the Bidirectional Separate Kalman Filters technique, which employs as its basis the Kalman Filter technique, a widely used approach in sensor's measurements correction. Moreover, its application in separate filters, one for each outlying area, exploits

the classification performed by the model and allows the filter to concentrate only on points which need a correction, avoiding so the correction of points which were classified as correct and the consequent misleading internal change of state. Finally, having the entire trace available, it is possible to apply two separate filters, for each area, going in opposite directions, reducing so the tendency of Kalman filters to maintain the original direction, when applying the correction, an approach that cannot usually be applied, given the online application of the technique that is generally performed.

5.4 GPSClean: an all-in-one application

The previous chapters introduced how it was possible to obtain a corrected version of a GPS trace, starting from the model trained with the collected dataset and applying then a correcting strategy.

As a last step in this thesis project, we decided to combine the outlined procedures in a set of scripts, called GPSClean, that can so perform the entire pipeline on a GPS trace, obtaining so a distributable Python package.

The first operation that needs to be performed is clearly reading the input GPS trace. We decided to read input traces provided in the GPX format, using the Python library `gpxpy`³ to parse it and obtain the timestamps and locations.

After that, the conversion module, previously developed, was employed to convert the coordinates to ECEF and to calculate the deltas between the various points. Next, the sliding window function is applied to obtain the segments needed by the pre-trained model.

When it comes to modelling, we decided to employ the TensorFlow Lite model obtained from the conversion step mentioned in section 4.4.2. This choice was motivated by the intention to maintain the application light, using as dependency for this step only the TensorFlow Lite - Runtime. The model is then used to derive the predictions for each point, applying always majority voting to combine multiple predictions for a single point.

Subsequently, points identified as pauses are removed, as explained in section 5.1. The last step is the correction of outliers, performed using the Bidirectional Separate Kalman filters on outliers, technique outline in section 5.2.5 and chosen as mentioned in section 5.3.

After the correcting procedure has been applied, GPSClean creates a new GPX file and track, always using the `gpxpy` library, and, after having added all points to it, exports the track to a new GPX file.

Moreover, a possible option of the application, managed using Python `argparse`⁴ library, allows the user to obtain as output not only the corrected GPS trace in the GPX format, but also a GeoJSON version of the original trace with included the annotations obtained as output of the model. The resulting GeoJSON trace can then be visualised and analysed using the Track Annotation web-app, outlined in section 3.2, which was used to collect the training dataset.

The overall process, implemented as a series of Python scripts, was bundled in a single Python package, available for download in the associated GitHub repository⁵ and installable through Python's standard package installer Pip⁶. Moreover, for more details, the source code of the resulting application can also be consulted at [33].

³<https://pypi.org/project/gpxpy/>

⁴<https://docs.python.org/3/library/argparse.html>

⁵<https://github.com/sbettid/GPSClean>

⁶<https://pypi.org/project/pip/>

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The goal of this thesis project was to explore and compare the application of machine learning methods to the field of GPS data filtering and cleaning.

Initially, we recognised how the need of filtering GPS data is acknowledged also by large player in the fields, who generally offer the possibility of processing and filtering the data, exploiting also large already collected datasets. However, the results of the offered approaches are not always satisfactory.

Moreover, we analysed existing studies investigating the issue, and it was possible to notice how most of them exploit geographical information or prior knowledge, for example knowing the original route or basing the cleaning on the underlying maps. For this reason, we decided to concentrate our attention on methods that do not involve the application of geographical knowledge and to focus on GPS traces collected while performing outdoor activities, which could so be less constrained in the movements and therefore harder to predict.

Initially, we acknowledged the lack of existing annotated datasets containing such GPS traces, namely datasets in which the errors have been explicitly marked. We therefore developed a web-platform that was used to collect a dataset, a process that resulted in 61 annotated traces related to various outdoor activities. The possible errors that could be marked were pauses, outlier points, points registered while being indoor and unknown errors, therefore errors not belonging to the previous categories. Moreover, it was possible to explicitly mark correct areas, to enrich the information provided with sequences of points which recorded the user's position correctly, as well as including some additional metadata, such as the activity type and the device used for recording it. As a second activity, we tried to develop a machine learning model able to distinguish between the aforementioned categories of points.

Our initial hypothesis was that recurrent neural networks could adapt naturally to the described problem, given their ability to learn time-related patterns. Some preliminary experiments, performed on a reduced dataset and with the goal to distinguish between various activity types, compared an LSTM approach with a more general multi layer perceptron (MLP) and a convolutional approach. Although all three approaches showed satisfactory performances, the results of the experiments confirmed our initial hypothesis.

For this reason, we focused on LSTM related approaches, comparing, through a grid search on selected hyperparameters, three different LSTM architectures:

- A vanilla approach[27], used to test a widely adopted LSTM structure
- An architecture described in the literature and that was used to classify, based on GPS data, the driving style[28]

- A custom designed architecture, which aims at understanding the non-linear relation in a bidirectional way in the first layers, reducing then gradually the number of neurons to reach the desired target.

During the comparison, only explicitly marked points were considered, along with the application of a sliding window approach, devoted to the creation of fixed length sequences of points that could then be evaluated by the model. Clearly, the width length and the step size were two of the hyperparameters the grid search took into account, along with the number of training epochs.

The results of the grid search outlined how the custom approach obtained larger accuracy scores when employed on 15 points sequences obtained with a step of two. Thus, this approach was selected for further training and optimisation.

After the data collection phase was completed, the obtained dataset was used to train and evaluate the selected architecture, using a three-fold validation. The results of this evaluation showed a mean accuracy, between folds, of more than 0.97.

It is worth noticing how the model was trained, at each fold, using the standard TensorFlow library, with the evaluation involving both the original model and its correspondent TensorFlow Lite converted model, obtaining consistent results. The adoption of TensorFlow Lite enabled us to run the final model, trained on the entire dataset, without the complete dependency of the standard library, enabling so its execution also on low-powered portable devices, allowing so mobile scenarios to be considered.

After obtaining a model able to correctly distinguish between the different types of errors, we decided to concentrate on possible correcting methods. Firstly, we decided to treat pauses as a "special" type of errors. In fact, points representing pauses should appear, in the ideal case, stacked one upon the other, given that the position of the receiver did not change in the considered time frame. For this reason, we decided to remove points belonging to pauses, averaging their position.

Regarding outliers, the second most common type of error in our dataset, after pauses, various correcting procedures were tested, including linear and spline interpolation, Kalman Filters based approaches and a correction method that employed the model and its gradients to correct outliers, resembling the adversarial attack technique used against convolutional neural networks.

We discovered how comparing correcting approaches on GPS traces poses important challenges given the absence of a clear objective metric since, to the best of our knowledge, its identification is still an open problem for the scientific community. For this reason, the comparison was performed visually, inspecting its results on randomly selected traces. We observed how, the bidirectional application of a separate Kalman filter on each outlier area showed the best results and convinced us in its adoption.

As a final outcome of this thesis project, the execution of the TensorFlow Lite converted model and application of the aforementioned correcting techniques, on pauses and outliers, were combined in a single implementation which resulted in a lightweight Python package, released on GitHub under the name of GPSClean.

6.1 Future Works and improvements

We identified various aspects of the projects that could be improved, starting from the dataset used for training the model.

As outlined in the previous sections, the dataset is composed by 61 traces, most of them located in the Trentino-South Tyrol region, possibly biasing the modelling result on the geomorphological characteristics of this territory. For this reason, future experiments could concentrate on enlarging the dataset, collecting more traces, as well as considering different areas, possibly also in different nations.

A second potential improvement, related to the dataset, is the usage of metadata. The web platform that was developed for data collection made possible the optional addition of some metadata related to the trace, such as the activity type and the device used for recording it. A potential development of the project could be the investigation of how the activity or device type influence the recording, connecting so different type of errors to a certain activity or device, exploiting this information in the detection phase.

Moreover, other machine learning architecture could be investigated for the detection phase, exploring so possible alternatives techniques different from the neural networks approaches considered in this study.

Furthermore, the definition of an objective metric to assess the quality of a GPS trace is still an open question and could allow a more objective comparison of correcting techniques, improving also this aspect of the pipeline.

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Appendix A

Annotation App - Functional Requirements

This appendix reports the functional requirements document written before the design and the implementation of the Track Annotation app. Not all functionalities were initially included in the document, which was then revisited until the final reported version that can be found below.

A.1 Introduction

This document represents a concise functional requirements' specification of the Track Annotation App, web-application part of my Master's Thesis on the automatic correction of GPS traces generated from mobile devices, such as smartphones or smartwatches. The development of this application, although not a primary objective of the Thesis, was necessary due to the lack of a dataset containing annotated GPS traces, which will so be collected through the Track Annotation App platform.

A.2 Purpose and scope

The scope and purpose of this document is to clarify and explicitly analyse the user and functional requirements associated with the system, before proceeding with the development and implementation of the different functionalities.

A.3 Assumptions and constraints

In order for the project to be successful, the following assumptions are taken

- Stability and constant availability of the deployment system
- Stability and constant availability of the external data store used in the system

Moreover, some constraints have to be enforced:

- Deletion of all personal identifiable information from the GPS input files

A.4 Functional Requirements

Following, the user and functional requirements are outlined

A.4.1 User requirements

Each user should be able to freely access the web app, without registration. Then, a simple button allows the user to load a GPS trace using the corresponding GPX file, which is then showed on the map using lines, points and markers. It is then possible to annotate it, namely:

- Select the starting point of the annotated area
- Select the ending point of the annotated area
- Resize an existing annotated area
- Delete an existing annotated area
- Once the annotated area is highlighted, it is possible to mark it according to the available annotations

Users can apply the aforementioned process multiple times to different non-overlapping areas of the trace. Once the annotation process have been completed, they can submit their trace and download it. Once the submit button has been clicked, the user is prompted with a screen offering him/her the possibility to provide an author name, specify the device used to collect the trace and the activity undertaken. Moreover, information on how to modify, access and download the trace afterwards are provided.

Once the user confirms, the system displays a quick URL, which can be then used to access/-modify the trace after the submission.

The quick URL allows the user to directly return to the trace, with the possibility to modify it and resubmit/download the modified version.

A.4.2 Functional requirements

Section/ Requirement ID	Requirement Definition
FR 1.0.	The system shall load a GPS trace and display it into the map
FR 1.1	The system shall accept only valid GPX, KML and GeoJSON files, namely files containing points, representing the locations, and associated timestamps
FR 1.1.1	The system shall parse the input file and display the GPS trace on the map in the form of points connected through a line, with starting and ending markers
FR 2.0	The system shall let the user annotate the loaded trace
FR 2.1	The system shall allow the user to select different non-overlapping sub-traces by clicking on the starting and ending point
FR 2.2	The system shall allow the user to unselect a previously selected sub-trace
FR 2.2	The system shall allow the user to resize an existing annotated area
FR 2.3	The system shall allow the user to annotate a certain selected sub-trace
FR 3.0	The system shall allow the user to submit the annotated GPS trace
FR 3.1	The system shall ask the user for additional optional information (author, device and activity)
FR 3.2	The system shall send the GPS annotate trace to the external data store and insert/update it
FR 3.3	The system shall provide a download option for the annotated trace, preparing an annotated file
FR 3.4	The system shall provide the user with a URL that allows the modification of an already submitted trace
FR 3.4.1	The system shall load an existing trace whenever a valid direct URL is used